

Deliverable 3.1 – WP3. HIKR data best practices and methodologies

EURAKNOS

*Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European
Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System*

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WP3 – task 3.1

Summary

Deliverable 3.1 deals with the issue of knowledge acquisition by Thematic Networks (TNs). Each TN sets up its Knowledge Reservoir (KR), to make knowledge in the form of specific contents available to the end-users (farmers, foresters and advisors).

At this stage of the EURAKNOS project, it was essential to identify and define the processes used by the TNs to compile knowledge content in the KR and then disseminate it to the end-users. This fundamental step helps to describe and define how to design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR). To achieve this objective, Task 3.1 focuses on the issue of knowledge acquisition by the TNs. Task 3.1 involved the organisation of a working group to assess the needs of the end-users and also to collect their specific expectations from the existing TN knowledge reservoirs.

Then in a second step, it was useful to describe the different steps of the knowledge capitalization process, an active process of capturing knowledge assets and making them available to end-users. Finally, additional recommendations related to practices emerge for future TNs based on the consolidation of knowledge from the working group on identifying recommendations for best methodologies and practices to select, collect and store data in a harmonised way in a HIKR, in addition to those already acquired during the Budapest workshop.

Deliverable 3.6 will go into more detail and elaborate on these recommendations to formulate technical guidelines for TNs by all the WP3 task leaders with contributions of all partners involved in WP 3.

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List of abbreviations

WG: working group
KR: knowledge reservoir
HIKR: High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
ICT: information and communication technologies
MS: member state
TN: Thematic Network
WP: work package
MA: multi-actor

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1. Introduction

‘The future of innovation in European agriculture and forestry is based on the improved (digital) exchange of best practices between farmers, researchers and advisors from different sectors and member states (MS).’¹ This statement represents a real challenge to which the EURAKNOS project must explore solutions to provide recommendations and solutions. EURAKNOS aims to reinforce the European Union agricultural knowledge base through the development of a blueprint for a Knowledge Reservoir (KR) that enables the farming/rural community easier access to best practices from all European Union H2020 Thematic Networks (TN).

WP3 of the EURAKNOS project explored the ways to design a high impact knowledge reservoir (HIKR) in a H2020 project context. The objectives were to define the best ways to collect, store and share information, knowledge and data-based and making outputs targeted to specific agriculture and forestry sectors and/or European regions. The KR methodology provided is supposed to strengthen the response to the end user's needs and to facilitate knowledge management and its sustainability.

A KR is a collection of materials, practices, instruments, methodologies and tools, which contribute to the use of innovative solutions for sustainable agriculture and forestry. A HIKR strives to maximize impact through the best content, structure and methodologies focused on urgent end-user needs. It provides the ways, channels and tools, to reach the end-user (farmer, forester, researcher and adviser).

To determine the harmonised and the best design and format for a HIKR to be used in projects such as TNs and other multi-actor H2020 projects, several steps were planned. WP3.1 was in charge of the first level, i.e. the best methodologies and practices to generate, select, collect and store knowledge and data as outputs of TNs.

The WP2 dedicated to a general overview of KR assembled within the H2020 TNs, showed the great diversity of information and communication technologies (ICT) solutions developed to ensure the innovation transferring. Format, design, type of data and the ways data are produced, collected and stored, appeared unlike and disparate. The user needs have been related but not often prioritised.

Therefore this WP 3.1 focused on knowledge capitalization, dedicated to making this knowledge accessible to the largest possible number of users. Knowledge capitalization aims to safeguard the knowledge acquired and held by users in the daily practice of their activity, mainly know-how and experience feedback.

¹ This reference is an internal formulation, which figures on the home page of the EURAKNOS website <https://www.euraknos.eu/>.

We tried to answer the fundamental questions through the organization of a working group that brought together different categories of field actors questioned on specific issues (knowledge needs, searching information habits, frequently asked questions). This consultation phase enables the identification of different social contexts (connected farmers versus unconnected farmers, awareness of digital tools, and autonomy in the search for information) to be taken into account to disseminate knowledge in line with the needs expressed.

The WG process aimed to follow the knowledge capitalization steps: from the collection and inventory of available content to the adaptation of content and formats to the dissemination uses. For this, it was necessary to take into account the context (cultural, socio-economic and relevant environmental considerations) that concerns the end-users and determines the end-users needs' (types and nature of the information sought: technological information, economic information, practical issues, peer to peer learning, etc.).

The description of these key steps enabled us to draw up a list of recommendations for the development of an effective and sustainable KR, referred to as a HIKR.

2. Statements and insights from WP2

The work done in the EURAKNOS Work package 2, more specifically in tasks 2.1 (Data impact assessment of TNs) and 2.2 (Design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past) showed a huge diversity of contents and websites (as knowledge reservoirs) developed by the different TNs projects. The objectives to deliver the available knowledge on TNs depend strongly on individual projects. Also, some weaknesses in the process to build a knowledge reservoir are found: lack of target analysis, deficiency of FAIR compliance and data maintenance.

The main outcomes and recommendations coming from the WP2 (deliverables 2.1 and 2.2) are as followed:

A great diversity of approach, therefore of contents and KR Current TNs have different websites with different IT structures, formats and contents, depending on the actors involved in the project, the topics, the sector, the targeted audience and countries and the outputs of the project.

Recommendation 1:

To be of high impact the results should not only be of high relevance to the end-user but also easily accessible and understandable, and this should be better facilitated. These concepts refer to the following FAIR principles:

The acronym FAIR² stands for **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**. Put (very) simply this means³:

- **Findable:** Make sure a knowledge object can be found and found again.
- **Accessible:** Make sure a knowledge object can be accessed (for example by downloading it) and that access is given to the appropriate person or system.
- **Interoperable** (more relevant for data but not only): Make sure that the knowledge object is represented or annotated in a way that allows it to be combined with other Knowledge Objects or data sets.
- **Reusable:** Make sure the Knowledge Object has suitable metadata explaining who by and how the Knowledge Object can be used (for example whether commercial use is permitted).

FAIR compliance has been assessed in the WP2 tasks specially tasks 2.1 and 2.2, as far as possible. Even if taken into account and been in line with FAIR principles is a really crucial point for data management, it was unfortunately not possible to systematically evaluate the respect of these principles for all knowledge objects produced by TNs.

For these main reasons, the team project in charge of setting up the Data Working Group decided to leave this issue aside when holding the WG. It was felt that this issue was not a priority at this stage and that it was better to focus on an assessment of the needs of potential users of the platform. Especially as this issue is much more related to the work of WP4 on the development of a prototype platform, which aims to integrate already existing knowledge objects produced by different TNs.

Recommendation 2:

When designing a KR, it is essential and fundamental to take into account the need and to satisfy the expectations of end-users. We must be able to know what type of content end-users expect and define the functionalities offered by the KR to direct end-users as much as possible and as well as possible towards suitable and interesting content.

From all the statements and insights, WP3 and in particular, task 3.1 will develop a rational methodology in a way to perform in designing a HIKR, investigating these main steps of the designing of a KR: identify the end-users, add basement of the content provision and storage, design the informatics framework and management system and contribute to the dissemination of knowledge and improve the impact.

Moreover, the risk of a top-down approach instead of a multi-actor approach was evaluated as an important weakness and a strong guiding thread between the different WP3 tasks. The implementation of the multi-actor approach in the different phases of the project, conceptualisation, implementation (initiation and execution) and post-execution was tested and formalized. By the end, two outputs will be provided: the main specifications for the next HIKR and the main recommendations for new TNs engaged in such a challenge.

² Wilkinson, et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

3. Methodology

3.1. Working group objectives and methodology

A 2-day participatory workshop (working group 3.1) was organised in Paris on 12th and 13th December 2019. This workshop was built on the outcome of task 2.2 ‘*design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past TN*’ and the discussions during the Budapest workshop (deliverable 2.5 ‘*Report of EURAKNOS workshop 1 in Budapest*’).

The working group (WG 3.1) was set up to identify recommendations for best methodologies and practices to select, collect and store data in a harmonised way in a HIKR. This group gathered different actors from researchers to farmers interested in innovation brokering. Various working sessions were conducted to specify the user needs in terms of knowledge and the best impact knowledge support. Regarding task 2.2 outputs, this workshop was able to identify areas for improvement and standardization. The detailed outline of the workshop can be found in annex A.

The knowledge exchanges involved in the TN can be figured out in this diagram.

Figure 1: end-user needs and link with TNs

- On one side, the 'knowledge users': farmers, foresters and advisers etc., enquire such depository in their daily professional life and are therefore looking for reliable sources of information adapted to their needs. Once this source of information has been identified, tested and approved, it could then become their agricultural "Wikipedia".
- On the other side, the TNs 'knowledge providers' create functional knowledge reservoirs and seek to share all their knowledge sources as much as possible, targeting as many users as possible.

The steps that separate user and TN are therefore listed here:

- 1) *End-users request: “I have a question”, “I am looking for information”*
- 2) *Evaluation of the content available in the KRs*
- 3) *What are your recommendations emerging?*

In between, barriers of communication occurs and slows the dissemination process, as well as social representations and materiality of practices, are central elements of change. In T2.2 overview, some access limits have been expressed such as the language used, skills and competencies requested, the lack of information maintenance (updating).

But how do these actors come to meet and establish a reliable relationship of trust?

To try to answer this question and thus identify the methods and practices to be implemented by the TNs to achieve this goal, we have reconstructed the steps that separate the user who is looking for information and a TN that proposes one or more practical solutions. We assess whether the needs expressed are in line with the offers provided by the TNs. Based on what we observe, then we can propose ways of improvement to considerably increase the impact of the TNs, in terms of approved and reference contents.

Then in the following sections, we will detail them and especially mention the contributions that were made by the participants in this working group.

3.2. Working group participants

The main objective to set up a working group is to bring together a diversity of actors involved in TN or aware of the multi-actor approach. In order to ensure that all participants could express themselves, the different workshops were conducted using several specific methods of participatory animation.

The WG was composed by taking into account several elements:

- *The function of the participants*: it was intended that this working group should be multi-stakeholder. To this end, a balanced distribution was ensured between different groups of stakeholders sought (farmers/foresters, advisers and policy makers as knowledge users and TN participants, researchers as knowledge makers).
- *Geographical origin*: as far as possible, an attempt was made to cover the whole of Europe to be able to take into account the geographical diversity, even if the Estonian delegation was predominant.
- *Fluency in English*: this is a necessary prerequisite to participating in such a working group but at the same time a major obstacle to mobilising a wide range of European farmers. The only respondents present were from Northern Europe.
- *Available contacts*: the list of KIP members assembled within EURAKNOS but also and above all by the contacts of the EURAKNOS partner network.

The Working group 3.1 was composed as follows:

Table 1: workgroup 3.1 participants

Affiliation - organization name	Profession	Country
Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board	Policy maker	Estonia
Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs, Department of Research and Development	Policy maker	Estonia
Agricultural Cooperative Society A Carqueixa	adviser	Spain
Koivakonnu OÜ	farmer	Estonia
ALLIKA TALU OÜ	farmer	Estonia
ABioDoc -VetAgroSup	document database manager	France
NUTRIMAN (TN) Terra Humana Ltd	researcher	Hungaria
European Forest Institute	researcher	Spain

We created a multi-actor group, bringing together policy makers, advisers, researchers, farmers and even a document database manager.

Regarding the composition of the WG was not to get a very strong statistical representation. However, high priority have been given to recruiting participants according to the target group they represent (farmer / advisor / researcher).

The programme followed by the WG is presented in detail in Annex A.

WG 3.1 was led by Patrick Sarzeaud and Maxime Marois from IDELE, as task leader of task 3.1, with the support of other partners involved in this task, namely: Nathan de Geyter (UGent), Ilse Rasmussen (ICROFS), Pille Koorberg and Hanna Tamsalu (ARC) and Dario Arias (USC).

Photo: all the participants of WG 3.1, bringing together experts and partners involved in EURAKNOS, a real MA group!

3.3. Characteristics of the selected potential targets

To carry out this characterization, we used the user personae, meaning the group put itself in the shoes of a:

- Researcher,
- Policy maker
- **Farmer and foresters**
- **Advisor**

We will retain only the last two categories of users which are our main targets to reach.

The persona exercise has been lead at the beginning of the working groups (series of different workshops) in a common way with the other WG. 4 groups from mixed WG were set up and were invited by a facilitator from the EURAKNOS team to reflect with a series of questions about the main characteristics of the 5 main categories of KR end-users (farmer - forester/advisor/researcher/policy maker/facilitator). In that way, the results (annexe B) from this common exercise will have shared among the 4 WP3 task lead and could be exploited individually by WG working in parallel. The user persona⁴ is a fictional character created to represent a user type that might use a site, brand, or product similarly. Personas are useful in considering the goals, desires, and limitations of brand users to help to guide decisions about a service, product or interaction space such as features, interactions, and visual design of a website. A user persona is a representation of the goals and behaviour of a hypothesized group of users. In most cases, personas are synthesized from data collected from interviews with users.

During all the workshops carried out by the working group, researchers and policy makers were taking into account potential target groups of users but it was more relevant to only focus on the priority end-user's target: farmers, foresters and advisors because these target groups seem to be the priority target for TNs.

In each WG, invited experts were supposed to act in the representativeness of their user types. For instance in the WG 3.1, the desk analysis exercise in the role of persona showed the importance of the user need.

➔ What did we learn about farmers/foresters?

Participants' positions about agriculture innovation, are described in table 3 how they position themselves:

⁴ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persona_\(user_experience\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persona_(user_experience))

Table 2: positioning of farmers and foresters on innovations

Topics	Verbatim
 Fear of new things	“What is that?”
 Investment of time, money	“Great, but how to apply it or pay for it?” “Will it save me time and money?” “Cost and payback?”
 Reproducibility/process accuracy	“It probably doesn’t work in practice.” “Has it been proven in practice? Show me!”
 Desire to stand out	“Not like dad did” even if “Traditional practices can be innovative” Need to challenge oneself “Let’s do it” “It’s adding risk.” “A hype”

We, therefore, realize that it is essential to overcome a certain amount of reluctance for the farmers to come spontaneously to seek information. To do this, it is essential to offer them the ideal support that will hold their full attention. We have the impression that we have no right to make mistakes; one bad experience is enough so a farmer doesn't come back for more information.

We need to ensure that the proposed content is presented clearly and simply, easy to use and understand in their own language/alphabet.

- Why should farmers/foresters be interested in TNs?

Table 3: interests in TNs for farmers and foresters

Topics	Verbatim
 Joining a community	“We all need each other” To meet like-minded farmers, to come outside of the farm
 Willingness to access available knowledge	Access to new knowledge/technology from other farmers and civil society

<p>User-friendly tool</p>	<p>Easy access to information</p>
<p>Search for solutions</p>	<p>Easy to set up Finding solutions to problems Finding sustainable measures Increase profitability</p>

- What are the reasons given for using a knowledge platform?
 - Search for approved practical solutions
 - Identified access means
 - smartphone, get info in less time (more efficient)
 - by people relaying information (advisers), because they trust the responsible organisations involved in the platform

- What are the barriers expressed for not using a knowledge platform?
 - Tools limitations
 - Not useful for them, no update of the content, too complicated (scientific language), too much text.
 - Too many requirements/barriers (login etc.)
 - No digital access (no computer, no internet)
 - Lack of investment in the search for knowledge: no time
 - Language barrier
 - not in their native language
 - the level of simplicity of the wording
 - Lack of trust: they do not trust the platform
 - Already have their network: they have a personal connection to input providers or other farmers
 - No awareness of the tool: they do not know the platform

➔ What did we learn about advisers?

- What are the main characteristics of these profiles?

They express interest in agriculture. They have a passion to inspire change. They want to share their experience and maximize the impact.

About their behaviour, they are promoters in innovation. Their currency is "It's great! Use it!".

The place of advisers is legitimized by the needs expressed by farmers. Advisers bring knowledge to farmers by sharing practices and leave with new ideas that enrich their advice.

- What can the TNs do for them?

Knowledge library-info: they always need to learn something new for their farmers' community. They are fond of sharing knowledge.

The following list of keywords is a good illustration of what advisers expect from TNs:

- Meet peers/compare
- Being a better adviser
- Getting something out of the farm (money, products, experience)
- Pre-made validation group
- Perspective on the world
- Don't miss out on things
- Find and promote solutions across the EU

- What can an adviser expect from a KR platform?

They expect to have more time to collect information through readymade resources and easy access in their language. They want to stay updated on knowledge (policy/new tools/tailored factsheets) that they cannot produce on their own, but they can trust.

They have high expectations about the implementation of a platform that would contribute to the growth of their community.

- What are the barriers expressed for not using a knowledge platform?

The main reasons for not using a knowledge platform are: not useful for them, no update of the content, too complicated (scientific language), too much text, no time, no computer, no internet, not in their language, bad usability and difficult to navigate.

Other reasons can be: they don't know the platform, they don't trust it and no cross-platform approach exists yet. For each field of agriculture treated by different TNs, it is necessary to go and consult each time the knowledge is hosted by each KR.

4. WG 3.1: topics covered and participants' contributions

All the subsections in this section are related to the work done by the WG. Each subsection reflects the topics covered and how we compiled the participants' contributions.

4.1. Temporality of user needs

A first workshop was led to get some answers regards to the two following crucial questions.
What type of question could a user ask to a KR?
What type of knowledge would a user like to find in a KR?

Preliminary investigation phase to be carried out by TN when setting up a KR: ensuring that the content to be offered is in line with the expectations of potential users. This is what could be called a market study, which, if carried out, contributes to the success of content dissemination by the TN.

Each farmer, forester and adviser, in their daily job ask themselves some specific questions. These questions can be classified with regards to the degree of reactivity that this requires for the implementation of the proposed solutions.

It is thus possible to define 4 degrees of reactivity:

- 1) Questions for 'today': a technical problem still unknown today occurs in a farmer. Then he needs immediate technical advice, in the form of a practical sheet that will enable him to identify the origin of the problem and to identify concrete courses of action that he can take now to continue his activity.
- 2) Questions for 'tomorrow': a farmer has learned that a crop disease is emerging in his region. He would like to know more about it from a technical point of view so that he can react if necessary.
- 3) Questions for 'next month': a farmer is planning to introduce a new crop that has never been tested before. He has had the opportunity to discuss it with neighbouring farmers. However, he is looking for a fact sheet to get a clear idea of the next crop project.
- 4) Questions for 'next year': are mainly strategic and/or topical questions, which require investments in time, money, etc.

It is therefore this approach that has been chosen to lead to the collection of the following information from the participants.

Table 4: positioning by users on a time scale of the knowledge required

Timescale	Farmers/ Foresters	Advisors
Today	Practical questions Buy & sell Management & new ideas: to be thinking now for a further future Keep up to date with legislation	Precise answers for specific (new) problems – <i>e.g. how to treat disease problem</i>
Tomorrow	Same as ‘today’+ Prices	Prepare for upcoming problems, <i>e.g. disease in the proximity likely to come to the local area – what to do?</i> Literature monitoring and foresight
Next month	Which subsidies are available? Was the year profitable?	Practical measures to prevent/mitigate damages of climate change (or other events) that are already here Involvement in network and expert groups to be reactive when needed
Next year	Exchange with others doing similar things/thinking in similar ways (e.g. invest in solar-powered feed drier): join and take part in groups of innovative projects How to start with organic farming What changes to make on the farm	Strategic measures to prevent damages of climate change (or other events) are expected to arise in the future Advice for self-sufficiency

The raw production that made it possible to construct this table is presented in Annexe B.

4.2. Evaluation of the content available in the KRs

Main recommendations and observations from the WP2 have been integrated into the methodological framework of tasks, i.e. the huge diversity of contents and sites developed by the different TN projects weaknesses such as lack of target analysis, a huge diversity of contents and sites developed by the different TN projects, deficiency of FAIR compliance, softness in informatics and data maintenance, especially in the working group agenda, a specific workshop was dedicated to offering the possibility to all the experts to navigate into different online knowledge reservoirs and sharing their relevant feedback and comments.

To define a need expression, a specific section of the workshop with WG has been organised to enable the collection of requests and attitudes upon such sites and knowledge reservoirs, opinions and perceptions. All the participants were informed by the work done in WP2 and the main results obtained.

It was proposed to the participants to consult the knowledge contents proposed by the KRs of the 3 following TNs:

- AFINET (<http://www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet/knowledge-cloud/search>)
- SMART-AKIS (<https://smart-akis.com/SFCPPortal/>)
- INNO4GRASS (<https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/dissemination>)

The evaluation criteria were not formalised in advance because what was important was to gather the participants' feedback on the content offered by the different knowledge platforms tested, as test users.

Thus, we start from what was expressed by the participants during the WG, which led to the compilation of the tables below:

Table 5: evaluation by farmers of TNs' contents

Farmer		
Criteria mentioned by test users	Observations by test users	Favourite of test users
Usability of the platform	Personalized access	Very useful and indispensable function to be integrated, provided a few lines of explanation on the proposed contents are included.
	Paying attention to the platform design to make the content attractive Little introductory text but it should be catchy. Attractive presentation of the different content categories	
	The user must not get lost while using the platform.	Tree structure remains present on the side
Search ability and accessibility	Ease of access to content: limit the number of mouse clicks and ensure display on a single page	When they go looking for content, they only want access to content produced for and valued by farmers not interested in information relating to the project, on the contrary, they find such information embarrassing
		Make sure the results are displayed: the most relevant first, limit the number of displays, if several pages: only the first one will be consulted, so you might as well limit yourself to a single page!
	Once the content is displayed, think about how to retrieve it.	Provide action buttons 'ready to use', 'download' / 'ready to print' 'Sharing'
Content attractivity	Videos first	Videos attract attention
Content recipients		Provide pictograms: ready to use for...

Table 6: evaluation by advisers of TNs' contents

Adviser		
Criteria mentioned by test users	Observations by test users	Favourite of test users
Translation	All content is available in English and most of the time only in English.	A major effort should be made to translate content into at least the EU languages.
Usability of the platform	Access defined according to their profile (adviser/farmer)	Very useful and indispensable function to be integrated, provided a few lines of explanation on the proposed contents are included.
Search ability and accessibility	Difficulties in quickly and easily finding out all the content by an available theme	Need to be provided with the content assessed as most relevant to a given topic

In terms of methodology, it would be interesting and highly recommended that the development of content put online by TNs be subject to an MA approach, i.e. that end-users be involved from the outset in the development of content, to provide their input on the content, validate the form and are fully involved in this process from the beginning. A farmer talking to a farmer always carries more weight.

4.3. Drawing up a list of criteria for an HIKR

To set up an HIKR, a list of criteria should be taken into account. The aim of this workshop was to test a non-exhaustive list of criteria to all the WG 3.1 participants to gather their opinions in two stages. In the first stage, they expressed themselves in their own opinion, then in the second stage, they expressed themselves by putting themselves in the shoes of a persona.

The first set of criteria was elaborated by the organization team before the WG.

The criteria are varied but correspond to elements to be taken into account to constitute a KR. When a TN seeks to build a KR, this TN must be able to answer a certain number of questions, which for the most part correspond to the list of proposed criteria.

The expression of the participants on these different criteria is shown by the orange banner, which makes it possible to report on the levels of opinion expressed (the thicker the banner, the more the participants agreed).

The list of criteria evaluated and selected by the participants is as follows:

Table 7: list of criteria to be taken into account in a HIKR

Criteria / arguments	Rating scale		
Target audience = profiling	Researchers/teachers	all	Farmers first
	[Redacted]		
Comments	Innovation brokers	Farmers organisations / Advisers / teachers	
	The participants are unanimous in mentioning that the priority target that is being sought includes farmers and advisers. This is a fundamental element to be taken into account, as it must be borne in mind that the knowledge made available by KR is intended for farmers and advisers.		
Information source Depends on quality standard and trust	Researchers	Advisers	Farmers
	[Redacted]		
Comments	The participants agree that a majority of the information comes from research work. They expect to have information from results validated by tests and approved by field trials and demonstration events. Before this knowledge can be transferred to the users, it is essential to put it in a format appropriate to the final recipients.		
Geographical origin	International	National	Local
	[Redacted]		
Comments	applicability	Taking into account geographical constraints and specificities: impact on the applicability of shared innovation	
	The origin of the source of information is not perceived as a constraint. On the contrary, it is an opportunity to open up and capture as many tested practical solutions as possible. On the other hand, it is on the transfer to the users that particular attention should be paid. A certain number of recommendations will have to accompany the proposed practical solution, which will have to mention the criteria of applicability (constraints and geographical specificities to be taken into account).		
Solution practicality	Scientific	Technical (not theoretical)	Practical, ready for use
	[Redacted]		
Comments	The participants are unanimous; they expect practical, technical and ready-to-use knowledge.		

Argumentation for benefits	none	Specific interests	Economical, environmental and social interests
Comments	<p>Taking into account the context of the applicability of the proposed practical solutions is fundamental.</p> <p>It seems appropriate to assign to each practical solution proposed (whatever their format: fact sheets, leaflets, videos, etc.) a global or individual score on predefined criteria (for example level of practicality, economic impact, environmental impact, etc.) which will enable it to be ranked and guide the user in his choices.</p>		
Ranking criteria 'Searchable' versus 'exploratory'	None	Languages and production	Technical needs (for end-users)
Comments	<p>One can easily define two content search behaviours and thus influence the provision of content:</p> <p>'Searchable': you have to enter keywords to access the content.</p> <p>'Exploratory': the user moves through the platform from the tree structure of the site.</p>		
Search engine/keyword searching	General	Intermediary	Technical
Comments	<p>The two criteria above are linked. The participants agree that the practical aspect of knowledge is the element to be emphasized as much as possible and that the indexing of the proposed documents should be done through the use of appropriate technical wording.</p>		
Format	Scientific paper	Technical leaflet (two-sided)	Video farmer testimony + specialized adviser // podcasts
		Recipe	Short summary // recipe
Comments	<p>In terms of format, participants expect to find a certain diversity, depending on the message to be conveyed and the target audience. It should be noted, however, that some formats are given more prominence than others. For example, participants expect to find technical booklets in a short format (only front/back) that provide ready-to-use technical advice in the form of recipes. They also highlighted videos that provide testimonials from farmers and specialist advisers and promote peer-to-peer learning. The use of a short video can be useful and necessary to promote a brochure or other approved material by the consortium of the TN.</p>		

Consultation frequency	Annually	Once a quarter	Once a week
Comments	It is not necessarily obvious to be objective in answering the question about how often the KR is consulted. In any case, what is certain is that it would be ideal to build user loyalty and that they consult this knowledge platform once a week. It is used that will provide the answer. In any case, it is the rate of consultation that will make it possible to evaluate the relevance of the contents made available.		
Platform updating frequency	Annually	Once a quarter	Once a week
Comments	To build user loyalty, it is important to regularly add new content. A quarterly update frequency seems reasonable. A little new on the front page, it is necessary to show that the platform is 'alive', to retain regular users.		
Consultation time (in the site per access)	1 hour	15 min	5 min
Comments	Researcher/adviser	Farmer	
	There is a different viewpoint depending on the users. However, it must be remembered that farmers are looking for practical information but do not spend much time in the consecutive search. This observation must therefore be taken into account to offer an ergonomic platform and suitable searchable media.		
Maintenance Updating for functionalities	Annual	Monthly	Permanent
Access	Total: no registration	Limited	Private: only with registration
Comments		First, access is limited to registered members. After one month, contents available for all	
	An interesting strong idea has been proposed which consists in limiting for a short period (one month maximum) the access to new content, only for registered user members. After this period, all content is accessible to all: registered and non-registered members alike. This is certainly an effective option to build user loyalty and at the same time offer them a more personalized selection of content.		

Language	English only	English + other	EU languages
Comments	There is consensus that the proposed materials should not be available only in English as they will not be consulted by farmers. The recommendation that is made is to provide for the translation of all the contents at least in all the languages of the TN, but it would still be necessary to invest in translation and to offer content in all the languages of the European Union.		
Contact details	LOW		HIGH
Author (provider of information) identification	Full name Organisation Email - country		
Comments	The platform user must be able to easily access contacts to find out more. Either these contacts are systematically mentioned in the content or they are listed in a specific section to be provided.		

The raw production that made it possible to construct this table is presented in Annex B.

To complete the previous list, other criteria to be taken into account were mentioned during the consultation with the WG 3.1 participants. However, these criteria are given for information purposes only, as they have not been thoroughly evaluated, unlike those mentioned in the table above.

- 1) **Lawfully identified knowledge:** criterion that refers to the notion of trust and approved content
- 2) **Browse:** it would be nice to have a simple platform on which you can quickly get an overview, without spending a lot of time searching to get an idea of all the available content and features.
- 3) **Seeing user feedback:** complementary criteria to the previous ones, indeed users will be sensitive to the evaluation made of the contents by other users. Seeing feedback from other users reassures and arouses curiosity, so using this can help to engage more end users. This system also makes it possible to better identify users' needs over time.

- 4) **Keeping up to date by a domain of interests / Use persona access:** two slightly different but complementary criteria. The participants would like the platform to allow personalized access according to the user's profile to target the information offered according to his or her areas of interest. Coupled with the previous criterion mentioned, these two criteria would make it possible to provide personalised support to users, which will be appreciated, thus being able to build user loyalty.

To complete more precisely the evaluation of the set of criteria, the participants were asked to add descriptive elements and expectations by the two categories of users addressed: farmers and advisors.

The main recommendations that have been made are summarized in the following two tables.

Table 8: farmers' point of view expressed by the participants on the list of criteria

Farmers	
Themes	Priorities highlighted by the participants
<p>Practicality</p>	<p>To circulate on the platform, define a coherent path The user needs to be referred and taken care of. In a maximum of 5 clicks, the user must reach information contents Clear information, contents ready to apply!</p>
<p>Maintenance and updating</p>	<p>To build user loyalty and increase user numbers through the sharing of testimonials from convinced users, it is fundamental to want to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - regularly supply the platform with new content <i>Minimum frequency: every month during the first year of operation to attract and retain users</i> - update the platform to implement new fundamental functionalities. <i>Minimum frequency: as infrequently as possible to cause as little disruption as possible to users who would otherwise get lost.</i>
<p>Approved contents</p>	<p>Plan to disseminate only content for which the information is validated and approved. The user needs reliability and trust.</p>
<p>Provide sharing tools</p>	<p>Information coming from other farmers (peer-to-peer learning). To provide tools to interact with other farmers (like a forum, chat-room) “your digital neighbour”</p>
<p>Content adapted to the target audience</p>	<p>Information understandable, not scientific, and not too simple: find a compromise that can be adapted according to the subject matter and also the message to be communicated.</p>
<p>Benefits <i>How much will I save?</i></p>	<p>The financial argument is to be put forward on the content supports. Before testing a proposed solution, it is strongly recommended to estimate its cost. It was also important to the participants to include environmental and societal benefits.</p>
<p>Language</p>	<p>Understandable for every European farmer and advisors. Decide country by country, is the information reasonable to translate to all languages, if 50% of users understand English, no need to translate to local language, to sort out where the translation is needed, or where the advisers can provide translations.</p>

Table 9: advisors' point of view expressed by the participants on the list of criteria

Advisors	
Themes	Priorities highlighted by the participants
 Practicality	<p>Scientific format but the possibility of also having content support for which knowledge has been vulgarised to make it more easily transferable and assimilable and thus help the adviser in his key role of knowledge transfer.</p> <p>Have access to a keyword search engine integrated into the platform</p> <p>Classification of content according to the technical requirements of users.</p>
 Maintenance and updating	<p>how to keep updated on the searched object (consultation time), keeping updated on areas of interest → subscription possibilities</p>
 Approved contents	<p>Information sources should be research, not only practice information.</p> <p>Take the research, what is already proven.</p>
 Provide sharing tools	<p>A big influence on the sharing of the most relevant content</p> <p>Adviser as an applicant to expand their peer community</p>
 Content adapted to the target audience	<p>Many advisers are also in farming as well</p> <p>Need registration: in the first instance, advisers will be more reluctant to register, it will be less of a dissuasive barrier for them, unlike many farmers. This necessary registration is the only way for them to have access to content tailored to their interests.</p>
 Benefits	<p>It must be possible to attribute to each content a technical note of applicability of the proposed solution, which will guide the adviser in his choices.</p>
 Language	<p>It is probably not necessary to have the language for each country – in many (small) countries, 50 % or more of the farmers – and mainly those that use the internet – can read English – and for the rest, the adviser will read and interpret the relevant material.</p>

5. The exploitation and management of knowledge by a literature review

Following the WG, the project team discussed the analysis of the contents, the basic principles of transfer and in particular the notion of capitalisation in the form of the following bibliographical review.

5.1. Introduction

The exploitation and the management of knowledge involve five operations: identification, creation, storage, share and use⁵. Behind each of these key steps lies a fundamental question.

<p>Identification → where are the possible sources? Creation → how to organize knowledge to adapt them to a given target group? Storage → How should knowledge be stored to make them accessible? Share → how to promote the available knowledge? Use → How to identify shared knowledge ambassadors?</p>
--

Application to the TN context

Identification

A TN makes an inventory of the existing and available knowledge on the subjects that concern it. One of the challenges for the TN is to know where the available knowledge is. Among the available knowledge, the TN must also ask itself what knowledge is useful and which will be used to propose content available to the targeted end-users.

Creation

This creation stage essentially involves taking over existing content that will be adapted to meet the needs of end-users.

Storage

For a TN, storage consists of creating a KR in the form of a digital library where the TN's productions are stored and available to end-users.

Share

Knowledge sharing focuses on the tools for sharing and using the knowledge made available. Knowledge sharing is one of the dimensions of knowledge management within a community of requesting users. The implementation of access to knowledge is a key factor in enabling individuals to take ownership of knowledge to make use of it.

Use

⁵ According to https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_management & https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Management_des_connaissances

This step involves the exploitation of available knowledge by the end-users. This step is correlated to the means, tools and dissemination channels that are used, as described in deliverable 3.3.

5.2. Basic concepts: definitions and clarification

Knowledge capitalization⁶ is the action of extracting, formalising and safeguarding knowledge acquired and held in the daily practice of activity.

TNs⁷ have two main aims:

- collecting existing scientific knowledge and best practices that are close to being put into practice, but not yet sufficiently ready for farmers and foresters to implement.
- translating this knowledge into easily understandable end-user material such as short, informative recommendations and solutions: ‘practice abstracts’, leaflets, guidelines and audio-visual material (photos, video clips, etc.).

The objective of TNs’ is to collect already created knowledge (capitalising step) and to format (creating new content step) and share it (dissemination step) in a way to make it more accessible to the end-users.

⁶ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Capitalisation_des_connaissances

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/agri-eip/files/eip-agri_brochure_thematic_networks_2016_en_web.pdf

At this stage, it is essential to define the following terms and the complementarity that exists between these different terms:

Figure 2: data, information and knowledge, some concepts to be distinguished ⁸⁹¹⁰¹¹¹²

⁸ According to the reference <https://www.knowledge-management-tools.net/knowledge-information-data.php>

⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Information>

¹⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data>

¹¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge>

¹² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Know-how>

From data to know-how:

All data passing through media go from individual to individual. The information must be used by the person to become useful information. Skills and know-how are dependants on the person’s ability to adapt.

To manage knowledge, it is, therefore, useful to dissociate the two concepts ‘information’ and ‘knowledge’ (which processes information, reacts and evolves). This is the first principle of knowledge management¹³, it has to answer these two questions: *what is there to know? Who needs to know what?* The formalization of knowledge is part of this problem: *‘what knowledge needs to be safeguarded?’*, *‘To whom should I transmit an expert’s knowledge and in what form?’*

5.3. Tacit and explicit knowledge

There are two main categories of knowledge¹⁴.

Table 10: presentation of the two main categories of knowledge

	Tacit knowledge	Explicit knowledge
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - belong to mental representations, to lived experience - combine innate or acquired skills, know-how and experience - is difficult to verbalize or formalize ➔ random transmission (e.g. when transmitting knowledge between an expert in a field and an apprentice). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - clearly articulated on a written document or in a computer system - appearing in tangible form (paper or electronic file), are physically transferable. They are then verifiable and reusable as with the knowledge contained in an encyclopaedia.
Main feature	Undocumented	documented
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> know how to plough a field with a tractor know how to harvest a cornfield 	<p><i>How explicit knowledge is created?</i> Writing an electronic document and posting it on a website</p> <p><i>How explicit knowledge is used?</i> Follow a detailed recipe step by step</p>

From tacit to explicit

New knowledge within an organization is always due to individuals. Indeed, innovation almost always stems from a tacit idea from an individual or a group of individuals, an idea that will have to be transformed into explicit knowledge (knowledge about), like a specification.

¹³ <https://www.knowledge-management-tools.net/>

¹⁴ According to <https://www.knowledge-management-tools.net/different-types-of-knowledge.php>

Figure 3: explicit and tacit knowledge in the context of TNs¹⁵

Challenge for the TNs:

The challenge is therefore to capture this tacit knowledge, channel it, and finally make it explicit so that it can be transmitted to the rest of the network.

The classic scheme would be to learn tacit secrets (public disclosure of local knowledge), translate them into explicit knowledge, standardize this knowledge into a procedure or manual, and exploit this knowledge at the individual level.

Figure 4: illustration of the real challenge for the TNs

¹⁵ According to <https://www.knowledge-management-tools.net/different-types-of-knowledge.php>

Figure 5: knowledge flow within a TN community

The transformation of tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge through a translation process (a codification process) is not neutral. The explicit knowledge elaborated is therefore not identical to the tacit knowledge related to the experience that one has sought to translate.

This is an important point of vigilance to keep in mind as it contributes to the success of knowledge transfer by TNs. A TN must ensure that the content produced and disseminated is in line with the needs and expectations of end-users.

Codified knowledge can take different more or less abstract forms and focus on ‘how’ and/or ‘why’. To achieve good codification then means to ask oneself what form of codification is appropriated to the given situation.

Codification process

This process moves from tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge¹⁶.

However, here are the issues (facilitates the transfer, reinforces the cognitive alignment of the members) and the limits of codification (costly in time and resources):

Figure 6: transfer and structure

Explicit knowledge spreads more easily if it is structured and its structure is shared.

Figure 6 illustrates the role of structure in facilitating knowledge transfer. Imagine that you want to transfer one of these two diagrams A or B to an individual without him/her having access to the image of the diagram. Which schema do you find easier to transfer?

The usual answer is diagram B. Just say or write that it is a square, each side of which is made up of 6 points, specifying the diameter of each point and the distance between them. It is indeed much more difficult to describe diagram A which represents a cloud of points.

Why is this?

Diagram B has a structure, the square, which is known by a very large number of individuals. Conversely, diagram A has no apparent structure. To be able to transfer it easily and faithfully, it would be necessary to create, for example, an orthonormal marker to locate each point by its coordinates (abscissa and ordinate), in other words, create a structure.

¹⁶ https://www.agecso.com/wp/bourbakem/codifkorg/#_ftn1

5.4. Knowledge production process

- **Principle of knowledge capitalization**

The figure below presents the general schema of the principle of knowledge capitalization applied to the context of TNs:

Figure 7: the knowledge management process adapted to the TNs context¹⁷

Detail of the different steps of knowledge management:

① Selection/identification of available sources of knowledge: knowledge acquired in the course of projects, through specific research work by 'knowledge maker' mainly the researchers to a lesser extent the farmers, foresters through the advisers.

② Knowledge capitalization step:

- Evaluation of content on several criteria: interest, relevance, reliability, repeatability, etc.

¹⁷ According to Nada, Matta & Ermine, Jean-Louis & Aubertin, Gérard & Trivin, Jean-Yves. (2001). How to capitalize knowledge with the MASK method.

- Development of content appropriate to the expectations of end-users researchers, farmers, foresters as 'knowledge users'.

③ Implementation of a KR, a digital library useful for online content storage

④ Provision of content, dissemination and promotion to end-users

⑤ Interaction with the 'knowledge users', to create a loop of permanent enrichment of the KR contents and to guarantee the sustainability of the proposed knowledge, which until now has certainly been lacking in the KRs constituted by the NTs.

- **What to capitalize on?**

The two types of knowledge we want to capitalize on are:

- Scientific knowledge resulting from all the actions undertaken in the field of research.
- Technical knowledge: all the means used to bring a project to completion.

- **How to capitalize on this knowledge?**

The capitalization process is specific to a given organization. Knowledge is explained and then formalized to be made available for exploitation by users¹⁸.

The parallel with TNs is easy to draw, all the more so by integrating the results of the workshops conducted with the WG participants.

Figure 8: knowledge capitalization cycle

¹⁸ According to Leroy, D. (2002). Knowledge management and projects' capitalization: a systemic approach. Paper presented at PMI® Research Conference 2002: Frontiers of Project Management Research and Applications, Seattle, Washington. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute

Step 1: Identify knowledge:

To identify the knowledge required by the TN as a whole if it is necessary to appoint a facilitator. His/her role will be to identify and collect needs. A preliminary work of identification of the knowledge needs must be carried out at the time of the design phase of the project. Then, during the life of the TN, it is advisable to plan to organise special events (e.g. specific workshops) to identify the expected knowledge supports.

Step 2: Collecting, formalizing:

A dual-flow process as shown in Figure 5 would be very useful.

It is necessary both to collect practical knowledge from the field (useful, used and recognized by the field actors) and also to collect basic research knowledge, which is intended to be transferred to the community of field actors.

At the very least, this stage is organised around the organisation of two MA groups:

- One that focuses on collecting practical knowledge from the field. The main task of this group is certainly to list the available knowledge as well as the supports, appropriate contents and tools for dissemination. It is also necessary to think about the flagship content approved by the user community. These contents will be used to disseminate the new knowledge acquired by the TN.
- One that focuses on the collection of basic research knowledge: the main task of this group is to identify what information is useful for the user community and to determine its form. It is at this level that there is the most work to be done to organize this knowledge transfer and invest in finding the right final content support.

The next step would be to set up a test group of end-users (farmers/foresters and advisors) so that they can express their feedback, particularly on the relevance of the contents but also on the adequacy between the level of understanding expected and the level of understanding experience.

Step 3: Validate, back up:

This step requires the appointment of a domain manager or expert.

Another pertinent point is the quality control of the knowledge produced and stored. For this, it seems essential to appoint a quality manager.

It could also be useful to allow and ask end-users (farmers/foresters and advisers) to qualify and comment on the resources they use and in which context. That can help other potential users to select the relevant resources and pay attention to them.

Step 4: Operate, make available:

This step involves the implementation of adapted and efficient communication tools. This performance is achieved at different levels, within the consortium but also in the constitution of specific MA groups.

Step 5: Ensuring updating, enrichment:

To be efficient in this step, it is necessary to identify a person responsible and in charge of this step.

- **By whom is knowledge capitalized?**

Knowledge is only created, shared and evolved through the people at the heart of the problem, who must be mobilized and motivated by a facilitator.

This is of capital importance. Knowing how to surround yourself with the right people, at the right time.

A TN seeks to capitalise on the knowledge and make it available to a greater number of people.

5.5. Direct application to TNs targets

Based on the concepts discussed in the previous part and also thanks to the contributions of the WG participants, it is then possible to situate the capitalization of knowledge in the context of TNs.

- **Farmers/foresters: a community of practice!**

TN is a group of informally connected people who interact, learn together on all aspects of their practices, share knowledge, build relationships and through this develop a sense of belonging and mutual commitment. This ongoing exchange creates a collective intelligence aimed at improving innovation within the group.

The functioning of a community of practice is based on four pillars:

- A team: a set of actors federated around the same objective, the same theme;
- People who share intangible resources;
- People who cooperate;
- A common culture and a system of common interest.

- **Researchers: a network of knowledge-based experts**

Scientific research is organized around a network of experts. This scientific research is part of the process of producing new knowledge. This is always done based on establishing the state of the art, which consists in searching for all existing information concerning the field of research and

synthesizing it. Thus, knowledge management is indispensable in helping, on the one hand, to better understand what already exists and, on the other hand, to better organize new knowledge in such a way that it is understandable and reusable by future generations.

- **The TNs: a community of interest**

A community of interest is a group of individuals who share either an identity or share experiences and concerns. It is made up of people who are personally affected by a common problem, either directly or in their environment. Belonging to such a community helps them to understand and interpret their condition and to seek solutions to problems they may encounter. A project group is a group of people, temporarily brought together for their skills, responsible for studying a project to respond to a specific problem, giving it a rapid solution and closely monitoring its implementation.

This definition emphasizes the pooling of skills, expertise and knowledge to respond to a given problem. This makes it possible, in particular, to develop the group's capacity for innovation.

A TN seeks to capitalise on the knowledge and make it available to the largest possible number of users. For more information see deliverable 3.3 'HIKR communication, dissemination & exploitation strategies' and deliverable 3.4 'HIKR multi-actor approach'.

6. Step by step to a HIKR

In this section, the description of the knowledge management process in the previous section was important to better target the recommendations to be made in terms of knowledge platform development and guide drafting.

6.1. Key steps to identify and to harvest knowledge

This part is devoted to the description of the first two major steps, before the constitution of a HIKR:

- 1) User need identification
- 2) Harvesting and co-generating knowledge

To visualize how these steps articulate with the other steps that make up the execution phase of the TN, all the WP3 task leaders met from 27 to 28 February 2020 and collectively developed the scheme below.

Figure 9: TN project execution: key steps

6.2. Items to be taken into account

To describe, the fundamental elements to which these two steps refer, the method of construction of a decision tree has been retained.

Thus, a decision tree has been developed to select data according to the project benefits and will emphasize the economically most sustainable knowledge applicable at a local/regional/European level. Cultural, socio-economical and relevant environmental considerations will be taken into account.

The objective of this decision tree is to present the different stages of the knowledge capitalization process. They will be described in two levels:

- **Needs content/knowledge:** what are the essential steps and recommendations we can give on this phase of the needs assessment process
- **Harvest content/knowledge:** what are the essential steps and the recommendations we can give on this phase of harvesting the most relevant knowledge content.

Figure 10: items to remember when assessing needs

Figure 11: items to remember when harvesting content

6.3. Needs assessment recommendations

This stage is a way to identify the needs of the end-users and also to identify what the end-users expect from the TNs' KR in terms of:

- kind of knowledge: type of subject covered (to be positioned on a time scale), topics related to the environment, related to current or future regulations or topics that provide answers on the socio-economic context
- format of contents: this format is interdependent on the subject matter and the target to which it is addressed

To assess these needs, several tools can potentially be used (survey, workshop, persona exercise...).

Before being able to build up a collection of content, it is necessary to take some time to make an inventory of all the available content. To do this, it is advisable to appoint dedicated people who will have a set of evaluation criteria, both quantitative and qualitative.

All the elements will be included in deliverable 3.6, a guide of recommendations for future TNs.

6.4. Harvest process recommendations

The 3 successive steps underlying the harvest process are:

- Production of content in line with the needs of end-users
- The issue of content storage
- And a quality aspect of the proposed contents.

All the elements will be included in deliverable 3.6, a guide of recommendations for future TNs.

6.5. Additional recommendations

In task 3.1, several steps were followed and based on:

- Exploitation and valorisation of WP2 achievements.
- Collection of stakeholders' opinions during a data WG to define the basis of building a platform. This work was the needs expression phase of potential future users of the platform.
- A bibliographical review on the capitalisation and transfer of knowledge to feed the design and the framework of a guide.

D3.1 – report on HIKR methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage

From all these steps, it is possible to identify some additional recommendations.

The knowledge capitalization process is ongoing. It starts at the start of the project and theoretically never stops. As long as the knowledge pool remains active, i.e. updated and administered by a resource person. As described above, it is, therefore, a dynamic and cyclical process.

Our role here is to list a certain number of criteria that are fundamental to take into account, to store knowledge and share it with users (knowledge users and diffusers).

In summary, the answers to the following questions constitute a list of useful recommendations for the design of a KR:

- What is the background?

To build, design and develop a KR, it is first necessary to define a context.

It is defined by the circumstances and conditions that are part of its environment.

- Who are the end-users, awaiting useful information?

This step consists of identifying the target users to be reached.

For TNs, these are farmers, foresters and advisers, as priority targets.

- What needs do we want to meet?

The setting up of a TN starts from a need, to work and exchange in a network on a precise, common theme.

The content of the different steps presented in figures 10 and 11 will be included in deliverable 3.6, a guide of recommendations for future TNs in the form of more detailed practical sheets.

- Summary of identified methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage

The following table summarizes the main recommendations and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage that could be retained in a way to set up a HIKR.

D3.1 – report on HIKR methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage

Table 11: recommendations for data generation, selection, collection and storage

Criteria mentioned by test users	Observations by test users	Most appreciated by test users
Usability of the platform	personalized access	A very useful and essential feature to be integrated, provided a few lines of explanation on the proposed contents are included.
	Paying attention to the platform design to make the content attractive. Little introductory text but it should be catchy. Attractive presentation of the different content categories.	Provide an easy way to give access to the platform in several languages.
	The user must not get lost while using the platform	Tree structure remains present on the side
Search ability and accessibility	Ease of access to content: limit the number of mouse clicks and ensure display on a single page	When they go looking for content, they only want access to content produced for and valued by farmers. Not interested in information relating to the project, on the contrary, they find such information embarrassing.
		Make sure the results are displayed: the most relevant first, limit the number of displays, if several pages: only the first one will be consulted, so you might as well limit yourself to a single page!
	Once the content is displayed, think about how to retrieve it.	Provide actions button 'ready to use'/'download'/'ready to print'/'sharing'.
Content attractiveness	Provide some content most relevant for users. Most users are excepted contents 'ready to use'. Videos first and very relevant factsheets.	Videos attract attention
Content recipients		Provide pictograms: 'ready to use for...'

D3.1 – report on HIKR methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage

All these feedbacks and these thoughts might be taken into account in the process of the platform's designing and have been taking account by the team in charge of the platform's designing.

7. Prospects

The design of a KR is inseparable from the MA approach, efficient communication and dissemination networks and adequate computer tools.

The development of a KR must be a fully MA co-designed approach. All these essential steps will be discussed in detail in deliverable 3.6, which is a practical guide of recommendations for future coordinators of thematic networks and also of MA projects. One of the aims is to capitalise on knowledge from different sources and share it with the greatest number of people, particularly among communities of advisers, farmers and foresters. Thus, in this guide, which want to be a practical reference for thematic networks, we aim to respond to these main challenges.

8. Annexes

Annex A: detailed workshop outline

Day 1 – 12th December 2019		
Time	Activity	Purpose & Method
8.30-11.00	Introduction plenary session Session 1	Introduction to Euraknos and welcoming exercise 5 min intro to WG3.1 Exercise 1: Persona body mapping
11.00-11.30	Coffee break	
11.30-12.30	Session 2: Introduction to Working Group 3.1	Exercise 1: Introduction: who is in this working group Method: Intro-exercise to identify who is in the room and capture experience (icebreaker exercise) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you consider to have in common with this group? • What do you consider to be your unique contribution to the group? Present and expand on the objectives of WG 3.1 (20 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context setting • General presentation of the results obtained in the previous step of the EURAKNOS project.
12.30-13.30	Lunch	
13.30-16.00	Session 3: Target request & Evaluation of the content available	Exercise 2: Target request from an end-user: ‘What type of question could I ask a KR? What kind of information would I like to find in a KR?’ <i>Session objective and method:</i> 4 groups of persona (researcher / policy maker / farmer / adviser) are using. All these personas are positioned in the context of their daily lives: they ask themselves several questions that require them to seek information. A time scale is defined in terms of the time required to implement the concrete action generated by the answer to the question. It is the question for today? Tomorrow? The next month? The next year? A vote with sticks will help to prioritize the main requests of each group. Exercise 3: Evaluation of the content available in the KRs <i>Session objective and method:</i>

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		Testing TN platforms: the tests were carried out as an expert in their daily function. We left out the persona.
16.00-16.30		Coffee break
16.30-18.00	Session 4: criteria to build a HIKR	<p>Presentation session on specifics recommendations got from Budapest workshop for TN</p> <p>Exercise 4: define the types of content adapted for a given target audience (first part)</p> <p><i>Session objective and method:</i> Ask the participants per subgroup according to their assigned persona to retain only 3 types of existing or ideal content (because of previous exchanges, work + consultation of KR) according to their relevance, at least adapted to the most adapted and for each content to bring out a list of arguments to produce and to share contents.</p>

Day 2 – 13th December 2019		
Time	Activity	Purpose & Method
8.30-9.00		Reflection and summary of work WG day 1 and explanation of the day 2
9.00-10.15	Session 5: An ideal HIKR related to end-users needs	<p>Exercise 5: define the types of content adapted for a given target audience (second part)</p> <p><i>Session objective and method:</i> Feedbacks on the list of criteria Put into the shoes of 4 personas (farmer/adviser/researcher/policy maker) and define the most essential criteria</p>
10.15-10.30		Coffee break
10.30-11.30	Session 6: Marketplace	Intergroup exchange – overlaps and synergies between the 4 working groups – time for cross-exchange
11.30-12.30	Session 7: WG3.1 Reflection consolidation, and way forward	Reflection on session 6: Identification of areas of overlap, things you learned, surprised to see frustrated In plenary consolidation and way forward Evaluation
12.30-13.00		Workshop end
13.00		Lunch

Annexe B: Presentation of examples of the raw productions of the Paris workshop

1) Persona exercice

SUMMARY		USERS				
	FARMER/FORESTER	ADVISOR	RESEARCHER	POLICY MAKER	FACILITATOR	
How did the _____ get to this position?	Through family from generation to generation, through marriage, as a new entrant, as part of large industry (a hired Farmer) Out of passion and interest A desire to be independent and create your own job Through access funds/own funding/EU funding As a way to generate extra income (forester - landscape) Independence, you can make profit and create a job	Agriculture interest, passion to inspire change Possibility after university As a way to generate extra income (farmer/forester) Wants to share experience, maximizing impact Forestry advisor (loves nature) As a hobby Not interested in doing an actual farming job Cannot handle pressure	Wants to understand the world, solve research questions and problems, validate practice to theory, achieve a personal challenge "Smartness"-academic: Good practice, publication, reputation Passion and curiosity Nothing else to do, external pressure/economy, good steady salary (private company) Status Meet like-minded people	Passion to "change the world", wanting to make it better, societal/social/Climate change Interest in agriculture, but not having practical experience Motivation from farming/rural development Practice policy vs career as a policy maker Through friends family network, job opportunity Steady job (civil service) Interested in policy/design/making research Curiosity Getting power	Interested in holistic approaches and social change It is a new role Innate skills Interested in people	
What kind of training did the _____ get?	A farmer can be born and raised on a farm Agriculture school, college/university Work experience, apprenticeship, on farm experiential training, learning from peers in working groups Compulsory environmental training Differs by country (qualifications in management) Self-training	Agriculture school + specialized courses, university/technical school, learning by doing Social skills Specialist - coaching Professional skills (people skills/communication/facilitation/practice experience) None	Master / PhD / post-doc Involved in agriculture, rural space environment Company training CPD (i.e. travel, seminars, conferences) On the job/learning by doing Multi-actor interaction Facilitation / presentation	On the job training University degree Public speaking University education Experience in agriculture Work placement / internship	Interested in holistic approaches and social change It is a new role Innate skills Interested in people	
What keeps the _____ up at night?	The weather Policy changes, policy responsibility, policy restrictions Supply chain, money, mortgage Problems with machinery, livestock health, conflicts (land use) Family, children/no children to take over the farm Climate change, sustainability, biodiversity - disease Lifestyle - motivation Thieves, poaching, protesters/trespassors Fire concern Service quality - using service	Deadlines Solving the farmers problems/crisis, calls from farmers Psychological support HIVe topics/GET health, KIPS Policy changes, regulation changes Worrying about losing clients Customer satisfaction, how to be paid for added value, will the farmers need me? Will I get my salary? Closing the gap between civil society and farmers	Runding funding funding (what happens next?) Research problems, model not working, not having solutions The next generation of scientists Need for publications, generating scientific impact Deadlines and publications Passion not done yet! Will this be useful/applicable/make a difference? Will I change the world? Have an impact? Social contact	Next election, next programming period Farmer strikes, negotiations, reforms, crisis, media, public opinion How to find: Solutions for problems/Divide funds/Deal with conflicting interest Finding policy makers at different levels Looking for advisory service Deadlines Budget Empathy with farmers - income Politics / politicians Industry pressure How to implement policy	Social dynamics in a group/network Funding of role How to deal with trouble makers, conflict/conflict management Financing pre-project Deadlines Meetings How to enable the process - tools to use	
When does the _____ feel good about his/her job?	When getting recognition - positive feedback - appreciation When the harvest is good - when everything is doing good When the prices are right - sustainability of business When having a good relationship with the customers When coming in contact with nature - being outdoor When having enough investment capital - cashflow When work goes according to plan (weather, livestock) When you can be proud of the business Flexibility of policies (what might mean innovation for some can be hard for others) Growth When innovation works	When farmers deliver change/innovate When getting trust from farmers (is doing good) When learning from the job When providing "good" support (training/boost) When the clients are satisfied Success of possibly reaching new clients Generating impact, making a difference Better salary Positive feedback from farmers Awarding ceremonies/recognition Number of visitors on field days	When work gets published (in high impact journals) and presented When having good results from farmers (it worked) When understanding the world When the results are used and impact is generated, make a difference/impact Increasing B-value/quotations/citations Recognition by peers and users / industry, Nobel prize Involvement in networks	Successful program, projects that succeed No bad news "When you go in the field and you see difference/solution for farmers", when you feel actors have positively changed Peer/actor recognition - minister Confidence / competence Integration and implementation of effective policies When a low/home changes Getting re-elected	Energy - Energize participants Positive feedback Impact Making a difference Group flow Unexpected results/rewards/recognition	
What could a quote of the _____ be about agriculture innovation?	"What is that?" "We need IT!" "Great, but how to apply it or pay for it?" "It probably doesn't work in practice." "Has it been proven in practice? Show me!" "It's adding risk." "Will it save me time and money?" "Cost and payback?" "Innovation is for rich/overconfident/efficiency obsessed value!" "Traditional practices can be innovative." "Not like dad did." "A hype!" "Managing forests together with nature!" "Will it bother what the neighbour does?" "Let's do it!"	"Too much!" "Opportunity for work" "innovation is a chance for business" "Opportunity to work on social innovation!" "Too much bureaucracy!" "If the farmers are too good at innovating themselves, we might be redundant!" "How can I tell this to the farmers use it?" "I don't understand it!" "It's great! Use it!" "How can I help and users apply it?" "Why make my life so difficult?" "Let's do it!" "Farmers have solutions, researchers have answers, advisors have questions!"	"Do we really need it?" "Is it really necessary?" "Important, but in my subject!" "Most important for food security" "Most important for climate protection" "A novel practice/technology which is evidence based, which finds a solution for the local supply chain which has an impact on important topics/actors" "I changed the world!" "Fund me so I can make a difference!" "In three years it will be applicable" "Of course you can do this on a real farm!" "My results gave farmers a better economy/environement" "More studies needed!" "Showing know-how" "It needs a systems approach!"	"Necessary!" "Solve great challenges!" "Digital is only a tool, not a solution!" "Innovation is a way to create rural development for ecological transition through programmes which solve societal/environmental challenges and add value!" "Yes comment!" "This is going to have impact, good for the economy, export and environment!" "How to measure impact?" "Can it help us make money?" "What are the risks?"	"Helped to make it happen!" "Does it really lead to transformation?" "Innovation is a reason to bring all actors together to have a positive effect!"	
The _____ should be interested in TNs because...	"We all need each other!" To stay updated, to get new ideas, to share experience, to build a network, to improve farm/forest, to have a positive impact, to find funding Easy access to information To meet like-minded farmers, to come outside of the farm Access to new knowledge/technology from other farmers and civil society Get information about legislation change Increase profitability Finding sustainable measures Finding solutions to problems A forester will not be interested in this	A marketing opportunity for advisors Collaborations, connect to farmers/advisors/researchers/policy makers/OCS Knowledge library-info, learn something new for "my" farmers, share my knowledge! Meet peers/compare Being a better advisor Getting out of the farm Pre-mode validation group Perspective on the world Don't miss out on things Find and promote solutions across the EU	To get info for research, to make connections (to multi-actors), to find evidence to advice policy makers, to converse with industry, to make new collaborations, to avoid duplications, to validate results To get back to the roots New needs for research to connect to EU-level New way to solve new research problems Platform for knowledge and creating impact Learning how to do it in practice Peer consultation/peer review Making research relevant and visible Promote uptake of results => no publication potential!	Feedback and validation from industry, this, farmers, detect policy blind spots Knowing the lobbies To be up-to-date with innovation, stepping from innovation to transformation, see policy in practice Higher level politicians only need key information, data (e.g. to evaluate the risks) Connect to actors and get out of your building/bubble Put weight to their policy by agreement Increasing impact	Because they play an important role in this To connect, share skills and find work To find an innovation broker To be more engaged To generate more knowledge impact	
What drives the _____ to use the platform? Or the knowledge reservoir?	Via smartphone on the job so you can get info in less time (more efficient), via advisor, intermediary, teacher, peers, because they trust the responsible organisations involved in the platform To solve a problem with validated/proven/demonstrated/practical solutions To save time, to meet one-another, to get recommendations from other farmers, to Because it is presented in a clear and simple way, easy to use no understanding in their own language/alphabet Because it is more accessible for forester?	They don't know the platform, they don't trust it Information conflicting with knowledge Bad usability/user-friendliness/UX/UI Difficult to navigate/learn/learn Differentiation of quality/source No cross platform approach	To find an overview, find info related to the topic (to conduct desk research), promote research, network, stay updated, get inspired, create impact Peer review/interaction To understand the uptake of similar approaches Low Technology readiness level (TRL) -> high TRL progress	Via smartphone To get into contact with the coordinator (not the platform), find relevant info on results/state of the art (via support teams), find experts, evaluate existing knowledge to drive new policies, screen information, assess how likely farmers are to implement new policies Through a separate policy maker space To find convincing stories from farmers	To look for partners (experts), find content, to make a difference, find work (challenges), find new ideas	
What could keep the _____ from using the platform?	Because it's not useful for them, no update of the content, too complicated (scientific language), too much text, no time, no computer, no internet, not in their language, they don't know the platform, they don't trust it Good experience with the content Because they have a personal connection to input providers or other farmers Too many requests (login etc.) IT/digital literacy	Because it's not useful for them, no update of the content, too complicated (scientific language), too much text, no time, no computer, no internet, not in their language, they don't know the platform, they don't trust it Information conflicting with knowledge Bad usability/user-friendliness/UX/UI Difficult to navigate/learn/learn Differentiation of quality/source No cross platform approach	The platform is not up to date, no scientific content, no detailed content, no knowledge / Awareness of KR, no validation of content Unclear convenience preferences of sources of information Bad usability Lock of time Not understanding practice Fear of plagiarism Knowledge conflicting Feeling above the knowledge level	Via smartphone To get into contact with the coordinator (not the platform), find relevant info on results/state of the art (via support teams), find experts, evaluate existing knowledge to drive new policies, screen information, assess how likely farmers are to implement new policies Through a separate policy maker space To find convincing stories from farmers	Lack of time Informal organisation Not tailored Searchable Inspiration Trigger for new ideas	

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GROUP 1	USERS				FACILITATOR	CUSTOMER
	FARMER/FORESTER	ADVISOR	RESEARCHER	POLICY MAKER		
How did the _____ get to this position?	Interest, you go to study? Family Independence, you can make profit and create jobs	Agriculture interest Not wanting to do an actual farming job Career development Finance Marketing impact Flexibility of the industry Additional income (farmers/advisor)	Education Wants to work with details Getting research questions To understand the world	Passion to "change the world" Curiosity Interest in agriculture, but not having practical experience Practical policy experience as policy maker	Interested in facilitator opportunities and social change In a network	
What kind of training did the _____ get?	Agriculture school Work experience A farmer can be born and raised on a farm Learning from peers in working group	Agriculture school - specialised courses Specialists	PhD Interested in agriculture Good science environment Conferences	On the job training University degree Public speaking	Facilitator training Being a specialist	
What keeps the _____ up at night?	The weather A change in prices Policy changes Market conditions Problems with machinery or animals	Deadlines Cuts from farmers Not having an impact Not being "right" results Policy changes	Research problems Funding (personal) Not having funding The next generation of scientists Need for publications, generating research impact	Not selected Not programming period Funding issues Not in field Solution for problems Climate funds Deal with conflicting interests Facilitating to create different levels Facilitating to create Facilitating to create Leading for industry sector	Social dynamics in a group/network Funding of the How to deal with trade makes	
When does the _____ feel good about his/her job?	When getting recognition When the market is good or the business is doing good When the price is high When having good relationship with the customers When coming to contract with the customer When having enough investment capital	When farmers follow change When getting out from farmers When working from the job When something "good" happen (training/help)	When work gets published When having good results from an experiment (it worked) Not failures When understanding the world	Success of program Not failures Projects that succeed		
What could a quote of the _____ be about agriculture innovation?	"What is that?" "You need IT?" "I need to have to apply it or pay for it?"	"This much / owner" "Opportunity for the world" "Not much for business"	"This really need IT?" "Is it really necessary?" "Opportunity for the world" "What important for food security?" "What important for climate protection?"	"Innovative" "Great great challenge" "Digital is a great tool, not a solution"	"Helped to make it happen?" "Does it really lead to transformation?"	
The _____ should be interested in TNs because...	"We will research other" Some objectives To get new ideas	Meet farmer A meeting opportunity for advisors Some objectives This was related to training Collaboration	To get info for research To get into the network To get into the room To make connections To find and share to advice policy makers To communicate with industry	Knowing the topics To get into the network Sharing from innovation to transformation High level and practical information This is the audience	Important roles in the Implementation Finding innovation leader	
What drives the _____ to use the platform? Or the knowledge reservoir?	Via smartphone on the job so you can get info in less time (more efficient) Via website, intermediary, website A problem	How much time to collect information	To find an overview To find information to help (to conduct desk research) To spread the word To connect	Via smartphone Get into contact with the coordinator (use the platform) Facilitating Find answers to a specific problem of the user (for support teams) A specific policy maker space	Lead for experts Find content Find partners	
What could keep the _____ from using the platform?	Not used / Confusion / Bad experience with the content Long range Not knowing the platform Not used / No time No quality of the content	Meet farmer	Time Not enough time to do No content / content No detailed content	Time Lack of interest Different time needs		

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GROUP 2		USERS				
	FARMER/FORESTER	ADVISOR	RESEARCHER	POLICY MAKER	FACILITATOR	
How did the _____ get to this position?	Farmer Inheritance Generation to generation Transition Access to labour/funding/EU/funding Passion	Farmer Horses Hobby farming Passion	Training and working experience	"Smartest" academic: Solid practice, publication, reputation Passion Values: practice vs theory Wanting to solve a problem Curiosity	Education from farming/level development Wanting to make it better Social/economic/structure change	Skilled by him Communication Leadership Goaling Resilience Diverse
What kind of training did the _____ get?	Farmer Practical training On-line experiential learning Conferences/management training Others in country (specialist/management) College/university	Farmer Learning in practice/experience College/university for horse courses Others in country (specialist/management)	Specialist coaching Professional skills (people skills/communication/facilitation/practice experience)	University education Company training CDO (i.e. free, webinars, conferences)	University education Experience in agriculture Work placement / internship	Teacher training Facilitation/training - CDO Leadership/coaching
What keeps the _____ up at night?	Farmer Money Weather Market agency Policy responsibility Family Climate Climate change Climate uncertainty Supply chain Policies and/or other control	Farmer Horses Fencing Risk concern Weather Supply chain (market vulnerability) Service quality - User service Business vs. lifestyle Sustainability	Deadlines Regulation changes Selling in 1/2y Why my product is being eaten How to be paid for added value	Research problem Deadlines Marketing pressures Data to be used Other topics	Deadlines Budget Budgets with farmers: income Policies / politicians Regulations Risks	Financing preparation Confidentiality management Deadlines Marketing How to enable the process - risks to use
When does the _____ feel good about his/her job?	Farmer Good practice / sustainability of business How well according to plan (marketing, livestock) Positive feedback Time to pursue / complete Public opinion / reputation Beating the competition Other kind of business	Farmer Wild animal management Sustainability & transmission of business Facility of practice under high heat Innovation for some can be hard for others Wider interest of business	Collection of clients Transmission and selling on advice Success of clients receiving new ideas	Results Innovation Funding Sustainability Final position Market acceptance/impact	"When you go in the field and you see difference/innovation for farmer" Market acceptance - innovation Confidence / competence Integration of practice When it has/hasn't changed When you feel action has positively changed	Energy - Energy participants Market feedback Market management Marketing efficiency Group time Unexpected results/feedback/reception
What could a quote of the _____ be about agriculture innovation?	Farmer "I probably don't work in practice." "Innovation" "Innovation is for rich and wealthy/agriculture/added value" "Innovation practices can be imitated"	Farmer "Innovation is a niche" "Innovation for some can be hard for others" "Innovation is for rich and wealthy/agriculture/added value"	"Innovation is a niche for business" "If the farmer are not good at innovating themselves, we might be redundant" "Openness to work on social innovation"	"A rural practice/technology which is evidence based, which finds a solution for the real supply chain which has an impact on important rural issues"	"Innovation is a way to create 'real' development for ecological transition through programmes which solve societal/ environmental challenges and add value"	"Innovation is a reason to bring all actors together to have a positive effect"
The _____ should be interested in TNs because...	Direct experience Building network High impact/visibility Easy access to information	Connect to farmers/specialists/researcher's/industry makers Knowledge transfer only Being a better advisor	Connecting to multi-actors New needs for research to connect to EU issues New with practice via research projects New collaborations New for knowledge and training impact	To research/practice on Connect to sector Out of your building/building Validation Feedback Referring	Work Engagement Connections Sharing skills Knowledge impact	
What drives the _____ to use the platform? Or the knowledge reservoir?	Time saving Need for specialist For marketing Cross sector dialogue Regional Building awareness of other farmers Recommendations of other farmers Through intermediaries and advisors	More accessible for farmers?	Short update on knowledge For feedback - entry New technological techniques	Proactive research Credit model Data enabled New information Curiosity - what's happening? Innovation Competition (passive)	Content / How processes Traffic message Screening of information	Having a difference Work New facilitation challenges New ideas
What could keep the _____ from using the platform?	No computer Time Language barrier Personal connection to legal procedures or other farmers Lack of awareness of value They are not communicative	Language Diverse representation Separability Trust issues - respect system Validation	No knowledge / awareness of IT Validation challenge Confidence/preferences of sources of information Usability Knowledge relates to non practical and generic When there are no needs	The specific Traffic message Open access/open source Time "Not part of their job" Transparency/efficiency in multi-actor User interface Validation of content	Lack of time Informed organization Not tailored Sustainability Relevance Trigger for new ideas	

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GROUP 3				
USERS				
	FARMER/FORESTER	ADVISOR	RESEARCHER	POLICY MAKER
How did the _____ get to this position?	Inherits farm Act as next owner Through marriage Large industry (old time farmer) An inspired choice/interest	Wants to share experience Wants a better or researcher (for additional income, not easy to be a farmer) Passion to inspire change Likes to communicate DSE Exchange on different practices	Pasion for a topic/for finding answers Nothing else to do Curiosity Good steady salary (private company research) Stress External pressure/economy Personal challenge Meeting like-minded people	Friends Family Network Career path Job opportunity Steady job (civil service) Begin to make a change Pulsion Hired by a politician (not required)
What kind of training did the _____ get?	On the job/in the family Apprenticeship Former schools Mandatory training Agriculture university / vocational schools	None Special skills for advising (facilitation) University/technical school On the job/industry Coaching/mentoring	University, possibly based on vocational training Methodology On the job/learning by doing Multi actor interaction Facilitation / presentation	Civil servant University degree (or less formal at a municipal level) Continual development courses
What keeps the _____ up at night?	Money/prices Bales Weather Caring Children/the children to take over the farm Pests/diseases Diseases	Will the farmers need me? Will I get the salary? Solving the farmer's problems/needs Closing the gap between civil society and farmers	Funding/funding funding (what happens next?) Research not done yet Will this be useful/applicable/make a difference? Publication/impact/peer results Will I change the world? Have an impact?	Media Deadlines Crisis Public perception Industry pressure Political situation
When does the _____ feel good about his/her job?	Job well done Crop/animals look good Snowed/daily Guardians of the land Being outdoors Self-organisation Tradition High yield/money	Making a difference Better salary Positive feedback from farmers Awarding/acknowledgement Number of visitors on field days	Increasing B-values/Equations/relations Recognised by peers and users / industry Presentation of work Salary & travel costs Publication in high impact journals Involvement in networks	Implementing effective policies Getting recognised Positive recognition
What could a quote of the _____ be about agriculture innovation?	"Will it raise me the time and money?" "Not like dad did!" "I usually do..." "You've been proven in practice! Show me!" "Will it bother what the neighbour does?"	"How can I sell this so the farmers use it?" "I don't understand it!" "It's great! Use it!" "How can I help and make apply it?" "Why make my life so difficult?"	"I changed the world!" "That's what I want to make a difference!" "In three years it will be applicable!" "Of course you can do this as a real farmer!" "My results gave farmers a better economy/development!" "There studies needed!"	"No comment" "This is going to have impact, good for the economy, export and environment" "Can't help, not make money!" "What are the risks?"
The _____ should be interested in TNs because...	Meeting like-minded farmers Come outside of the farm Access to new knowledge/technology from other farmers and civil society Get information about legislation change Having a positive impact	Learn something new for "my" farmers Invited to a network Getting out of the farm Peer-to-peer validation group Share my knowledge/learn from peers/compute Perspective on the world Don't miss out on things	Learning how to do it in practice Avoid duplication Realisation Peer consultation/feedback Validation Making research relevant and visible	Put weight to their policy by agreement Data (e.g. to evaluate the risks) The demonstrating new policies in practice Feedback from industry Define policy objectives Implementing policies Involving impact
What drives the _____ to use the platform? Or the knowledge reservoir?	Validated/proven/demonstrated/practical solutions Trust in platform responsible organisations Presented in clear and simple way (video) Own language/ foreign diplomats Recommendations by peers	Ready made resources/ready access Not able to produce such tools on their own Knowledge base in one platform - validated Own language Unbiased information - trust Recommendations by peers	Depends on level of information Understanding uptake of similar approaches Feasibility/own results Low technology readiness level (TRL) -> high TRL progress Learning how to demonstrate	Evaluation of existing knowledge to drive new policies Assessment of how likely farmers are to implement new policies
What could keep the _____ from using the platform?	Missing internet access No time Too much non-scientific language Too abstract Things that are not relevant Requirements/barriers (login etc.) Practices that are not transferable	Missing internet access Not relevant information/not suitable Information conflicting with knowledge Difficult to navigate Difference of quality/language	Not understanding practice Fear of algorithms Knowledge conflicting Being too casual / free Feeling above the knowledge level	Ignorance of its existence Scientific language No time Lack of understanding practice as theory

GROUP 4				
USERS				
	FARMER/FORESTER	ADVISOR	RESEARCHER	POLICY MAKER
How did the _____ get to this position?	Spillover Personal passion For a forester also complementary income (ecotourism)	Wanted to farm Inherited advisor (Dutch nature) Dutch a farmer/forester As a hobby	Curiosity Wanted to farm/forest Science / passion Increase the scale of the art	Interested in policy/design/making Curiosity To make a difference
What kind of training did the _____ get?	Self-learning Forestry Master's degree Higher education (this depends on the country)	Advisory services Learning by doing (informal) Higher education (formal advisor) Family	Master / PhD / post-doc	higher education
What keeps the _____ up at night?	Income (weather, markets) Optimal management Neighbour conflicts (land use) Diverse pressure/risk Policy restrictions	Customer satisfaction Customer relationships Negotiations	Publications Funding Deadlines/expectations Social context	Politics How to implement policy Public opinion Brexit
When does the _____ feel good about his/her job?	Higher yield Higher prices Innovation works Appreciation	Generating impact Increasing innovation When the farmers are happy	When experiments work -> SURVEIL When publishing a paper and getting citations When the results are used and impact to generate	Increase results following implementation of policy
What could a quote of the _____ be about agriculture innovation?	"Gorgeous and risky" "Let's do it" "Cost and payback?"	"Farmers have solutions, researchers have questions, advisors have questions"	"Sharing know-how" "It needs a systems approach"	"How to measure impact?"
The _____ should be interested in TNs because...	A farmer will not be interested in this solution (not self and promote) Networking Sharing Increase profitability Finding sustainable measures Finding solutions to problems	Contact with OGS Exchange solutions across the EU Find solutions across the EU Find knowledge and expertise	Research ideas Promote uptake of results -> no publication potential	Have ideas for policy Policy implementation across EU State-of-the-art -> To build on
What drives the _____ to use the platform? Or the knowledge reservoir?	Via an advisor Finding solutions to problems Easy to use/understand That other users use it	Communicate building (creating a positive atmosphere) Gaining feedback Easy to use Know about the platform Trust the know-how	Know the state-of-the-art Research ideas	Know existing projects/results Policy implementations Scientific proof Convincing stories from farmers
What could keep the _____ from using the platform?	Digital literacy No internet Language Cost Time	Time No cross platform approach Bad usability/user-friendliness/UX/UI Language Cost Need to search	Too applied Not relevant Lack of scientific rigour/proof	No time Not enough scientific proof Not finding relevant policy Not knowing the platform content

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2) Target request exercise

I HAVE A QUESTION FOR

PERSONA	TODAY	TOMORROW	NEXT MONTH	NEXT YEAR
FARMER	DO I SELL MY ANIMALS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WHAT ARE THE BEST FEEDS? WHAT ARE THE BEST PRACTICES NEXT WEEK? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WHAT SERVICES ARE AVAILABLE? WHAT IS A PROFITABLE COW MILK? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WHAT ARE THE BEST PRACTICES FOR THE NEXT YEAR? WHAT ARE THE BEST PRACTICES FOR THE NEXT YEAR? WHAT ARE THE BEST PRACTICES FOR THE NEXT YEAR?
ADVISOR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide answers on a new specific problem (e.g. animal health or a disease) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide answers on a new specific problem (e.g. animal health or a disease) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide answers on a new specific problem (e.g. animal health or a disease) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide answers on a new specific problem (e.g. animal health or a disease)
TEACHER				

D3.1 – report on HIKR methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage

3) List of criteria to build a HIKR exercise

